

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #FAIRprinciples, #FAIRsharing, #FAIRdata #Trust, #FAIR indicators, #EOSCinPractice

Guiding Infrastructure Governance And Controlled Vocabularies Requirement (GIGAR-V)

A concerted effort by the TU Wien Library (AT), ERINHA AISBL (FR), DataCove (AT), Natural History Museum Vienna (AT), reNEW Copenhagen University (DK).

The EOSCFuture.eu/RDA open calls

The open calls managed by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) with funding from EOSCFuture.eu aim to bring data initiatives closer to EOSC and provide EOSC with expertise, tools, best practices, and standards from the global research data community, with a total million Euro reserved to fund over 65 grantees over 12 open calls.

The Project Involved

The Project was supported under the second RDA Open Call for cross disciplinary science adoption grants and implemented by a consortia comprising the TU Wien Library (AT), ERINHA AISBL (FR), DataCove (AT), Natural History Museum Vienna (AT), reNEW Copenhagen University (DK).

The GIGAR-V team involved experts in terminologies, vocabulary management, registry software, and APIs, as well as members of standardization organizations with a deep passion for interoperable data and the data service landscape. In addition to their collaborative efforts on semantic artifacts and quality management, they collaborated across various scientific domains, including Biodiversity, Spatial Data (Environmental & Earth Observation), Informatics, Stem Cell & Pathogenic Medicine, and Language Models for Text Mining.

The key goal of the project revolved around tackling the intricacies of incorporating "individual" extensions into existing vocabularies while maintaining versioning, provenance, and quality assessment. The project's software functionalities were carefully designed to seamlessly facilitate this holistic approach. Comparison and collection of requirements will validate this and yield valuable generic recommendations for the scientific community.

Chris Schubert

Head of Media Management and Library-IT, Vienna University of Technology - Library

"Through collaborative efforts within our dedicated team and in alignment with EOSC, we've endeavored to bridge cross-disciplinary gaps and establish a standardized semantic framework. Our work acknowledges the diverse needs of experts from various fields, aiming to provide a transparent and unified solution for the evolving landscape of data analysis and AI advancements."

The Research Community

As the GIGAR-V team members come from diverse and unique scientific disciplines, they may have different backgrounds and areas of expertise. Despite these differences, they have similar needs and encounter analogous challenges are when dealing with semantic artifacts (such as terminologies, vocabularies, etc.). The use of these semantic components fosters a shared interest in terms of learning from and sharing knowledge and best practices across respective disciplines. However, the target audience pertains to three main groups: a) data creators, who receive guidance on enhancing the interoperability of their data by employing controlled vocabulary and published terminologies; b) scientific domain ambassadors, for example, standardization organizations or efforts; c) software developers, who have incorporated technical specifications and requirements to ensure alignment with domain necessities and the established standards from organizations like W3C and technical committees such as ISO.

The Challenge

For interoperable data services, explicitly-defined data variables are crucial for usability, aligning with FAIR principles. Poorly-aligned semantic resources, though, complicate cross-disciplinary use. Despite progress, the terminology field faces new challenges like multilingualism, sustainable concepts, and reuse. Unified strategies are needed for vocabulary definition across research areas. Challenges include completeness variations, monolithic frameworks, and limited curation. Software designs for semantic artifacts must tackle data quality requirements

Keywords:

1. #EOSCinPractice, #RDA, #semanticartifacts, #interoperability, #terminologies, #FAIRprinciples, #datagovernance, #standards

Useful tips & tricks

The main aim of this project is to enhance recommendations for a software registry concept used in scripts and implementations, while considering cross-domain requirements. Solutions deployed aim to:

- Streamline reference concept assignment, including vocabulary registration, curation, and provenance;
- Facilitate terminology co-creation with a clear governance framework;
- Enable W3C-compliant knowledge representation in ontologies;
- Enhance visibility and accessibility of interconnected research data through Knowledge Graphs

Benefits and impact

EOSC establishes a robust research data infrastructure environment through its dedicated research and implementation agenda. From our standpoint, the technical implementation of software and management practices yields a significant advantage: the tools and services developed within EOSC are not confined to R&I projects; instead, they find broader utility in cross-disciplinary contexts and align with various infrastructure services. This extends to EU Data Spaces, Global Earth Observation Monitoring, and the reuse of small-scale, in situ data. The process of garnering consensus on technical specifications and requirements involves effective communication and collaborative discussions with research initiatives like RDA and CODATA. This approach, in our view, is commendably transparent and open.

Why do I need RDA?

As an independent, global platform RDA provides a forum and inclusive mindset to share experiences, discover and provide knowledge, and show case a broad range of research data and infrastructure. RDA also covers aspects of the existing standards landscape and detailed issue statements of daily scientific tasks. Personally, I've received several supporting actions from RDA, like the RDA Adoption Stories, Bloggs, Webinars, as well as the Plenary stage, which helps my team get involved and take these benefits back to our "small" community in Austria.

Useful material related to this story

eoscfuture-grants.eu

rda-alliance.org

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC establishes a resilient and familiar research data infrastructure environment through its dedicated research and implementation agenda. From my perspective, the advantageous outcome of the technical software implementation and management rules within EOSC is that the focus of tool and service development extends beyond R&I projects, encompassing a significantly broader cross-disciplinary usage and consensus that extends to other infrastructure services like EU Data Spaces. Achieving agreement on technical specifications and requirements involves effective communication and collaborative discussions with research initiatives such as RDA and CODATA. In my view, this approach is commendably transparent and open.

Across disciplines

The essence of the GIGAR-V initiative lies in acknowledging cross-disciplinary factors. Our focus revolves around terminologies, which, within this context, entails establishing semantic content that inherently remains confined to specific domains. Professionals such as Earth scientists, biologists, and chemists create and maintain their semantic resources based on individual preferences. GIGAR-V aims to comprehend these unique requirements, pinpoint shared needs and challenges, and thereby encompass existing standards concerning registry items.

As the utilization of cross-disciplinary data grows – by data analysts, language models, or through techniques like text mining, machine learning, and the burgeoning AI field – the demand for a consistent and transparent semantic layer becomes imperative. This is precisely where terminologies step in to fulfill this role..

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